

INTERVIEW GUIDE

No	Question
Affecting	
1	How do you feel when departing and arriving at the hospital?
2	How do you feel when walking to the ODC room and undergoing a health check?
3	How do you feel during chemotherapy treatment?
4	How do you feel when experiencing distractions during chemotherapy?
5	How do you feel when chemotherapy treatment has ended?
6	How do you feel when preparing to go home or to the foundation?
7	How do you feel during the trip home or to the foundation?
Visual	
1	What did you observe from the time you departed until you arrived at the hospital?
2	What did you observe while walking towards the ODC room and undergoing the health check?
3	What did you observe during the chemotherapy treatment?
4	What did you observe during the experiment with multisensory stimulation?
5	What did you observe after the chemotherapy treatment had ended?
6	What did you observe when preparing to go home/to the foundation?
7	What did you observe during the journey back home/to the foundation?
Auditory	
1	What did you observe (hear) when departing and arriving at the hospital?
2	What did you observe (hear)when walking to the ODC room and undergoing a health check?
3	What did you observe (hear)during chemotherapy treatment?
4	What did you observe (hear) when a distraction occurred during chemotherapy?
5	What did you observe (hear)when chemotherapy had ended?
6	What did you observe (hear)when preparing to go home or to the foundation?
7	What did you observe (hear) during the trip home or to the foundation?
Haptic	
1	What touch sensation did you feel when departing and arriving at the hospital?
2	What touch sensation did you feel when walking to the ODC room and undergoing a health check?
3	What touch sensation did you feel during chemotherapy treatment?
4	What touch sensation did you feel when a distraction occurred during chemotherapy?
5	What touch sensation did you feel when chemotherapy had ended?
6	What touch sensation did you feel when preparing to go home or to the foundation?
7	What touch sensation did you feel during the trip home or to the foundation?
Smell	
1	What did you smell when departing and arriving at the hospital?
2	What did you smell when walking to the ODC room and undergoing a health check?

No	Question
3	What did you smell during chemotherapy treatment?
4	What did you smell when a distraction occurred during chemotherapy?
5	What did you smell when chemotherapy had ended?
6	What did you smell when preparing to go home or to the foundation?
7	What did you smell during the trip home or to the foundation?